

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction of older subordinates

Nosheen Nawaz

Lecturer and PhD scholar in the Institute of business management and administrative sciences, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur.

Email: nosheen.nawaz@iub.edu.pk

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6753-2576>

Dr. Syed Muhammad Javed Iqbal

Associate Professor in the Department of leadership and Business management (Institute of Business Management and Administrative sciences), The Islamia university of Bahawalpur

Email: javed.iqbal@iub.edu.pk

Received on: 16-10-2021

Accepted on: 18-11-2021

Abstract

One of the most peculiar hallmarks of this century's workplace transfiguration which is influencing employers around the globe is evident in age diverse workforce. The present research is a step forward in understanding the constituents of a non-normative work group discovered as a by-product of the age diversity and merit based promotion and selection criteria pertinent to the ultramodern 21st century. The non-normative workgroup which forms the focus of this study consists of the younger supervisor-older subordinate dyad. The present study was aimed at identifying the factors which influence the job satisfaction of the older subordinates working in an age incongruent relationship with a younger boss. The hypothesized impact of age difference, LMX relationship quality and perceived organizational justice on job satisfaction of the older faculty members in public sector universities of Punjab (Pakistan) was investigated. The impact of ageism as a moderator on the hypothesized direct relationships was also checked. Primary data on the study variables was taken on a structured questionnaire from 207 older subordinate faculty members using judgmental sampling technique. The data was analyzed using PLS-SEM technique in smartpls version 3.2. The results of the analysis reveal that age difference significantly negatively influences job satisfaction of the older faculty members. Job satisfaction of the older subordinates is found to be strongly predicted by procedural justice and LMX relationship quality. Ageism was found to moderate the relationship of job satisfaction and LMX quality.

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

The results of the study can be utilized by the organizational behavior researchers to further extend their work in the domain of relational demography specifically related to age inverse supervisor and subordinate dyad. The study is not only helpful to guide the future research, but also, aids the practitioners in better understanding of the older employee when he reports to a younger boss. This enhanced understanding can help in effective decision making and management of the older employees in organizations generally and in academic institutions specifically.

Keywords: age inverse relationship, job satisfaction, LMX relationship quality, organizational justice

Introduction

In the past, employees who were younger had been supervised by older employees, but this culture (behavior) has changed by certain trends in the recent years with creation of non-traditional dyads consisting of older subordinates and younger supervisors (Yang & Matz-Costa, 2018). A lot of companies have initiated merit based selection and promotions' system in an effort to enhance performance and reach the heights of excellence. This change has led the younger workforce to strive hard and leave older workers behind them in the path of career progression (Chiang & Birtch, 2007).

Demographic rearrangement of population has also given the younger employees a chance to be in supervisory positions. In western countries there is a greater ratio of older population so policies are redefined and older employees are retained by the organizations beyond their usual time of retirements and this allows for greater chances of new younger generation supervising them (Peeters, Marga, & Loek, 2012). The trend of older employees being supervised by younger managers has also been witnessed in some non-western specifically Asian countries like Pakistan (Khan, Salman Fazal, & Siddiqui, 2020) where the labor force contains higher proportion of younger population (59.71% of labor force lies between age 20 to 44 years) (PBS, 2018) and therefore, more instances of younger people in supervisory positions are found.

These recent changes have given rise to a new dyadic relationship in which the supervisor is younger than the subordinate (P. Cappelli & Novelli, 2013). The biggest challenge in this context is to have older workers having successful work relations with their younger supervisors (Kollmann, Stoeckmann, Kensbock, & Peschl, 2019). This age inverse dyadic relationship has led the researchers working in the field of relational demography to probe investigation about the possible consequences of this new composition of supervisor-subordinate.

This study is conducted in this context to examine the age inverse supervision in relation to work related outcomes specifically job satisfaction of the older subordinates. The study is imperative as it was suggested that, in order to effectively cope up with the challenge of managing the new age-inverse dyadic compositions of the supervisor and subordinate it is necessary at first place to identify the critical factors (Stöckmann & Kensbock, 2020) which may influence the work outcomes of the members of the dyad.

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

Statement of the Problem

In a dyadic composition in which supervisor is younger than subordinate, the older subordinate is often associated with problems which may in real be a result of violation of age norms in organizations (Miller, Carliss, & Orlando, 2020). In such situation older subordinate's age and status seems dissimilar and this results in older employees responding differently (Martinson, Brian, John, DeLeon, & Katherine, 2020). Smith, Wanda, and Vernard (1994) found that problems arise because of differing age beliefs. It was found that older subordinates being supervised by younger managers were engaged in demotivated work change behavior, higher absenteeism (Perry, Kulik, & Zhou, 1999), increased turnover and decreased integration in their work teams (Lau, Lam, & Salamon, 2008).

Hampered employee job satisfaction (Malangwasira, 2013) and increased level of burnout were also found in such relationship (Al-Zu'bi, 2010). In this emerging dyadic composition in which supervisor is younger than subordinate, research suggests that older subordinates and their younger supervisors both feel distrust and have negative attributions for each other which in turn hamper their performance and work related outcomes (Cappelli, Peter, & Novelli, 2010).

There have been calls to conduct research on the role played by age and the influence it has in workplace (Kulik, Ryan, Harper, & George, 2014). Moreover, it has been suggested that contextual factors beyond emotional suppression must be studied in age inverse supervisory dyad in the hope to help in bringing positive outcomes in the organizations (Kunze & Menges, 2017).

Traditional mechanistic organizations were more hierarchal and used to follow status and career norms but new organic organizations which are flatter have downplayed the traditional career progression and role norms. However, the possibility and hope is there that the career and status norms are malleable (Posthuma & Campion, 2009).

This hope gave the researcher an avenue of further research in this field. This research is conducted to analyze an important outcome i.e. job satisfaction as it may be influenced by age difference, quality of leader-member exchange relationship and organizational justice.

Research Questions of Study

The research was conducted with the objective of answering the following research questions:-

Q1: What is the impact of relative difference in the age of younger supervisor-older subordinate dyad, LMX relationship quality and organizational justice on the job satisfaction of older subordinates?

Q2: Does ageism moderate the relationships of age difference with job satisfaction and LMX relationship quality with job satisfaction?

Significance of the Study

The present research is significant because of the following reasons:-

- Age which has always been treated as an unnoticed and neglected background feature because of its believed indifferent position (Lawrence & Barbara, 1996) is a significant contributor or creator of the organizational context (McCarthy & Keegan, 2016). The present study is significant since it treats age as a salient feature which may result in behaviors

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

different from the usual organizational context.

- Unlike earlier studies which have been carried out in developed countries (Kunze & Menges, 2017), the present study is conducted in the less developed region of Pakistan.
- The present study makes significant contribution by identifying the factors which can foster job satisfaction of the older faculty members in the higher educational institutes.
- Previous research points criticism on the LMX theory for not being investigated in the realm of varying contexts (Anand, Hu, Liden, & Vidhyarthi, 2011). Although LMX theory has been studied in the higher education leadership context in the past (Lanier & Dequies, 2021), the present study makes a significant contribution in the LMX theory research by studying the impact of LMX relationship quality in the non-traditional organizational structure context.

•
Literature Review

1. Employee relative age with supervisor and job satisfaction

Research on age and job satisfaction suggests a positive link between both suggesting that job satisfaction of employee increases along with his age. In this instance, older workers exhibit more job satisfaction as compared to their younger counterparts (Ghazzawi, 2011) since they have more experience, lesser expectations and more relaxed mind. Likewise, research in the similar stream, suggested that older employees were more satisfied with their jobs because they had lower level of expectations as compared to younger workers (Glenn, Norval, Charles, & Weaver, 1985). This implies that the link between age and job satisfaction is influenced by expectations held by older employees which can therefore be one possible antecedent of job satisfaction in older employees.

Since job satisfaction is a critical employee attitude because of its vital linkages with work and general outcomes (such as lower absenteeism, better performance, lower turnover intentions etc.) so the need to study and explore the antecedents of job satisfaction increases in all employees generally and in older ones specifically (Cohrs, Abele, & Dette, 2006). One important variable in the road of exploration of antecedents of job satisfaction in old age is the age itself as it is an important demographic variable which brings with itself different expectations, hopes and prospects not held by younger employees (Wignall & Best, 2004). In the context of this study, it is relevant to mention that although some researchers have witnessed that job satisfaction increases with age (Ghazzawi, 2011), it may not be the case when the older worker is reporting to a much younger boss since older people may evaluate the situation differently and perceive it negatively because of unmet or under met expectations from the job (Cabelkova, Abrahám, & Strielkowski, 2015). Also, the research on job satisfaction and age provides evidence that job satisfaction of employees fails to go beyond 49% irrespective of their age group (Ghazzawi, 2011). Therefore, many causal relationships concerning antecedents to job satisfaction are still open for further investigation (Malangwasira, 2013).

Deducing from the above literature and adhering to the aim of exploring the antecedents of job satisfaction in older employees, this study (which is targeted at older employees working with a younger boss) takes job satisfaction of older employees as a dependent variable which is assumed to be influenced by the relative age difference between an older subordinate and a younger boss.

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

H1: There is a significant negative impact of relative difference in the age of younger supervisor-older subordinate dyad on job satisfaction of older subordinates.

2. Employee relative age with supervisor, ageism and job satisfaction

In a situation characterized by age relevant negative stereotypes, older employees in “age prominent” situation are most likely to face discrimination. Being supervised by a younger boss is comparatively a lesser observed practice which makes it an “age salient/prominent” situation for older subordinates.

More recently, it was suggested that older employees who were working under the supervision of a younger boss perceived more discrimination. It was argued that the lesser age of the supervisor made the situation more prominent age wise such that the older subordinates felt being “behind schedule” (Reeves & Michael, 2013). According to theory of implicit career timetables, work related outcomes (such as organizational commitment, job satisfaction etc.) of the older subordinates (who feel themselves behind schedule) are influenced. A summary of research on diversity suggests that greater age difference between the superordinate and subordinate results in lesser levels of job satisfaction on subordinate’s part (Green, 2005).

Combining the above given arguments it can be deduced that a possible explanation behind the influence of age difference between the supervisor and older subordinate on job satisfaction can be the perceived discrimination by the older employees.

H2: Ageism moderates the relationship between relative difference in the age of older subordinate and younger supervisor dyad and job satisfaction of older subordinates.

3. LMX relationship quality and job satisfaction

One of the studies pointed out that LMX is crucial as it acts as a buffer between the demographic differences between the members of the dyad and job satisfaction.

LMX is central and bridges the gap between demographic differences in the dyadic relationship between a leader and follower to job satisfaction. According to similarity attraction paradigm, people are attracted towards similar others. The notion was supported in a research study focusing on age difference between supervisor-subordinate dyad which claimed that dissimilarity in demographic characteristics specifically difference in age of supervisor and subordinate results in low quality exchange relationship between the supervisor and subordinate and it has the tendency to influence job satisfaction of the subordinates. In other words people are more comfortable and satisfied while working with others whom they feel are comparable to them (Malangwasira, 2013).

On the other side, the importance of job satisfaction prevails since it is found to promote positive attitudes and behaviors towards others and organization thus helping the organization to excel in achievement of goals (Bellou, 2010, p. 12).

H3: There is a significant positive impact of LMX relationship quality on job satisfaction of older subordinates.

4. LMX relationship quality, ageism and job satisfaction

Research on LMX theory suggests that dyadic relationships of different qualities are vital with regard to stereotypes. If a subordinate experiences and perceives being stereotyped as

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

trustworthy and valued by his manager or boss, he will be willing to exert more efforts towards pleasing his manager (Franklin, 2015) resulting in better quality of LMX relationship and job satisfaction which is found to increase in such conditions (Golden & Veiga, 2008). In the opinion of another researcher, the way subordinates act and interact with others in the organization is influenced when employees are known by their managers on the grounds of the stereotypes held about them within the boundaries of the organization rather than being personally known (Leonardi, Huysman, & Steinfield, 2013).

It was found that LMX relationship quality is extremely negatively influenced when supervisors hold age based stereotypes in their minds about their older subordinates and the victims of the stereotypical behaviors show poor performance and contribute less towards the organization and give poor quality work to their manager (Yakoub, 2008) possibly because of their decreased job satisfaction (Bos, Donders, Bouwman-Brouwer, & Gulden, 2009). On the other hand, it was found that when managers avoid stereotypes, the opportunity to expand job satisfaction of employees increases with development of strategic relationships of older subordinates with the organization and leader (Bornay-Barrachina & Guerrero-Villegas, 2014).

H4: Ageism moderates the relationship between LMX relationship quality and job satisfaction of older subordinates.

5. Perceived organizational justice and job satisfaction

More recently, the relationship between perceived organizational justice and job satisfaction has gained greater attention of researchers (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001). Researchers have suggested that the perceptions of fair treatment help employees to be more satisfied in their jobs and organization in general. The perceptions of employees about different types of organizational justice influence job satisfaction in different ways (Lind & Tyler, 1988). There is also some support in literature which suggests positive relationship between procedural justice and job satisfaction (Suliman, 2007).

Literature cited above suggests relationship between perceived organizational justice and job satisfaction, therefore, what shapes the perceptions of employees regarding organizational justice becomes a matter of indispensable interest.

In a meta-analytic study about the antecedents and correlates of organizational justice, it was argued that the perceptions of organizational justice may be influenced by the attributes the perceiver possesses for example his age, race, gender etc. (Cohen-Charash & Spector, 2001). One of the important yet unchangeable personal attribute held by employees is age. Therefore, the salience of age in analyzing organizational justice perceptions and underlying job satisfaction cannot be ignored especially in this era which is characterized by increasing age diversity in organizations (Tan & Nasurdin, 2011). However, a look at the academic literature suggests a shortage of research on the drivers of job satisfaction across various age groups (Kooij et al., 2013). Over all, it can be argued that the perceptions of organizational justice vary from person to person depending upon their age. Organizational justice perceptions are found to influence job satisfaction which also varies in older and younger employees.

H5: There is a significant positive impact of perceived organizational justice on job satisfaction of older subordinates.

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

Conceptual Model and Discussion

Figure 1: Conceptual Model showing the links between age inverse supervisory relationship and Job Satisfaction

Research Methodology

In order to test the hypotheses, primary data was collected from older faculty members (who report to a younger boss/chairman/head) of the 26 public sector universities working under the umbrella of Higher education department Punjab (Pakistan) on structured questionnaires whilst using convenience sampling to locate the respondents of the study. The questionnaire was developed with the help of the scales which were used by the previous researchers to measure the same variables in their studies on relational demography. The instrument which was developed for achieving the objectives of the study was presented to a panel of specialists from the Institute of Business, Management and Administrative Sciences, The Islamia University of Bahawalpur. The panel suggested minor recommendations which were incorporated in the instrument for its validity. The panel confirmed that the instrument has face and content validity i.e. not only the wording, language and sentence structure of the instrument was appropriate, but also, the content of the instrument was accepted for its ability to measure the thing it must measure for this research. The scales were adapted with necessary modifications which were considered appropriate for the current research. The collected primary data was analyzed using SEM through Smartpls version 3.2.

Findings

Descriptive statistics from the survey indicate that there was a greater ration of male respondents as compared to female respondents who took part in the survey with the number of male respondents reaching 157 out of a total of 207. Statistics indicate that 60 lecturers, 118 assistant professors, 12 associate professors and 17 professors responded to the questionnaire. The number of the older subordinates who were being supervised by a younger boss had a greater ratio of assistant professors, although, a minimum number (i.e. 12) of associate professors was also found.

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

Assessment of Measurement Model:

It is important to observe the results of the measurement model before the assessment of the structural model when using the PLS-SEM technique:-

A. Indicator Reliability and Construct reliability: Indicator loading of all the constructs was found above the minimum acceptable range of outer loading i.e. 40. According to Henseler, Ringle, and Sinkovics (2009), an indicator showing outer loading value of >.40 may be retained when it helps in achieving the desired composite reliability and AVE (average variance extracted).

The composite reliability of all the variables was seen to exist within the acceptable range i.e. ≥ 0.6 (Henseler & Sarstedt, 2013) and Cronbach's Alpha values of all constructs are above the acceptable range of 0.7 (Hair *et al.*, 2013; 2014).

B. Convergent Validity and Discriminant Validity: The convergent validity of the constructs is tested through Average variance extracted (AVE) and discriminant validity is checked using HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio of correlations). The AVE (Average variance extracted) values of all the constructs are above 0.50 which is the minimum threshold for acceptable AVE (Hair, Ringle, & Sarstedt, 2013). Ageism is the only variable which has an AVE of 0.442 which is below 0.50 but this too is acceptable according to a researcher who suggested that an AVE of less than 0.50 can be accepted for a variable having composite reliability value higher than 0.60 (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). The composite reliability of ageism was 0.844 so an AVE of 0.442 is acceptable in case of ageism.

Henseler, Hubona, and Ray (2016) suggests that if HTMT scores lie within the confidence interval value of +1 to -1, it can be derived that the discriminant validity has been established. The HTMT values lie between +1 and -1 thus indicating that discriminant validity is established.

Assessment of the Structural Model:

The assessment of the structural model is done by performing bootstrapping and blindfolding in smartpls 3.2. The following tables reveal the results of bootstrapping and blindfolding performed in Smartpls 3.2.

a. Assessment of Collinearity:

All the variables in the model are checked for multi-collinearity since the presence of collinearity between variables in the model can yield inflated or misleading results (Wang *et al.*, 2022).

Inner VIF values	
	Job Satisfaction
Age Difference	1.768
LMX quality	2.885
Procedural Justice	1.864
Distributive Justice	2.764
Ageism	2.486

The table given above reports the inner VIF (variance inflation factor) values. As it can be seen from the table that all the VIF values are between 1 and 3 so no issue of collinearity is

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

suspected among the variables. The values of VIF are below 4.0 (Hair et al., 2013) so structural relationships in the model have no tendency to bias the regression results.

b. Assessment of direct relationships and moderation effects:

The detailed results of the structural model assessment are given in table given below:-

Hypothesized paths	Beta (β)	Standard Deviation (SD)	T statistics	P Values	R ²	Effect Size (F ²)	Q ²
Age difference → JS	-0.126	0.053	2.357	0.019	0.641	0.025	0.350
AD → JS, Ageism (moderator)	0.074	0.049	1.513	0.130		0.010	
LMX quality → JS	0.255	0.071	3.589	0.000		0.063	
LMX → JS Ageism (moderator)	0.125	0.049	2.559	0.011		0.031	
Procedural Justice → JS	0.514	0.061	8.483	0.000		0.395	
Distributive Justice → JS	-0.134	0.072	1.866	0.062		0.018	

The table illustrates that the exogenous variables are capable of producing 64.1% of variation in job satisfaction as the value of R² is 0.641. Another important medium to assess the direct paths of all exogenous variables to predict job satisfaction is Q². The value of Q² as shown in the figure is 0.350 which indicates that the model has the predictive relevance. The values of R² and Q² indicate that the model has acceptable fit and predictive relevance.

The statistics given in the table make essential inferences about the study variables. It shows that job satisfaction is negatively influenced by the difference in the age of older subordinate and younger boss (β=-0.126, T=2.357, F²=0.025, p<0.05). LMX relationship quality significantly positively predicts job satisfaction of older subordinates working under a younger boss (β=0.255, T=3.589, F²=0.063, p<0.05). According to the results related to organizational justice impact on job satisfaction it can be seen that procedural justice significantly positively predicts job satisfaction (β=0.514, T=8.483, F²=0.395, p<0.05), however, the impact of distributive justice on job satisfaction is not found significant (β= -0.134, T=1.866, F²=0.018, p>0.05).

The results reveal that job satisfaction is most strongly predicted by procedural justice and leader-member exchange quality with beta values of 0.514 and 0.255 respectively. Age difference has a significant impact on job satisfaction of older subordinates but the impact is negative which means that as the age difference between the older subordinate and younger supervisor increases, job satisfaction of older subordinates decrease.

Ageism was not seen to moderate the relationship between age difference and job satisfaction (β =0.074 p=0.130), however, ageism is identified as moderating the relationship of LMX quality and job satisfaction (β =0.125, p=0.011). The effect size of this moderation is calculated through F² which equals .031 and lies in the acceptable range suggested by Cohen

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

(1988). According to a researcher, a moderating effect with $F^2 > 0.02$ and < 0.15 is small but it must not be considered negligible as even the smallest interaction effect can prove to be substantial under some moderating conditions so if the beta values are significant and meaningful, any moderation effect with $F^2 > 0.02$ must be considered significantly meaningful (Chin et al. 2003, p. 211).

Discussion and conclusion

Q.1 Is there any significant negative relationship between the relative difference in the age of younger supervisor-older subordinate dyad and job satisfaction of older subordinates?

The results of the study suggested that older workers show greater job satisfaction (Abrams, Swift, & Drury, 2016) as compared to their younger counterparts, however, this study suggests that the older the worker is in relation to his supervisor the lesser his job satisfaction is. The result of the this study are supported by another study which suggested that status incongruence resulting from directional age difference between a younger supervisor and older subordinate has the tendency to influence the job satisfaction of the older subordinate negatively (R. K. Miller, 2020).

Q.2 Does ageism moderate the relationship between the relative difference in the age of younger supervisor-older subordinate dyad and job satisfaction of older subordinates?

The result of the analysis suggest that ageism does not moderate the relationship between relative difference in the age of older subordinate and younger supervisor dyad and job satisfaction of older subordinates.

The findings of our study related to the insignificance of ageism as a moderator may be attributed to the Self-identity theory. According to the theory, older subordinates may have self-identified themselves; therefore, they do not give any weight to ageist beliefs that may be surrounding them as they become less important to them. Another possibility is that perceptions of age related status differ from culture to culture and nation to nation and in non-western cultures old age holds status of dignity and respect (Levy & Macdonald, 2016), so the effect of ageism as a moderator is less likely to be seen.

Q.3 Is there any significant positive relationship between LMX relationship quality and job satisfaction of older subordinates?

The result of the primary analysis indicates that there is a significant positive impact of LMX relationship quality on job satisfaction of older subordinates. The analysis suggests that even in the unusual setting of being supervised by a younger boss, the job satisfaction of the older faculty members increases when the subordinate-supervisor relationship quality is higher. One of the possible reasons for the positive impact of LMX relationship quality on job satisfaction of older subordinates was suggested by a researcher who argued that age leads to creation of better perceptions about LMX relationship quality when older age is culturally linked to respect and honor. In such conditions, older workers perceive better job satisfaction as a result of better LMX relationship quality they experience (Stephenson & Jacqueline, 2017).

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

Q4. Does ageism moderate the relationship between LMX relationship quality and job satisfaction of older subordinates?

Results suggest that ageism moderates the relationship between LMX relationship quality and job satisfaction of older subordinates. Findings of our research are supported by the similar early research in this context. It was suggested that negative effects of age discrimination (such as job satisfaction) in the workplace are dependent on the support employees receive from their colleagues and supervisors (Levy & Macdonald, 2016). This support networks shape dyadic relationship between supervisor and subordinate which in turn creates high or low quality leader-member exchange relationship. Thus, the link of leader-member exchange relationship with job satisfaction of older employees is contingent on the perceptions of ageism held by the individuals.

Q.5. Is there any significant positive relationship between perceived organizational justice and job satisfaction of older subordinates?

In the quest to answer the above mentioned question, data was collected on two dimensions of perceived organizational justice i.e. perceived distributive justice and perceived procedural justice. Two sub questions were designed in this lieu:

Q5A. Is there any significant positive relationship between perceived Procedural justice and job satisfaction of older subordinates?

Q5B. Is there any significant positive relationship between perceived distributive justice and job satisfaction of older subordinates?

The results of the primary data analysis suggest that job satisfaction of the older faculty members is significantly positively influenced by procedural justice, however, the impact of distributive justice on job satisfaction of older subordinates was not found significant.

The results of the present study partially confirm previous research (Laith, Jameel, & Ahmad, 2019) on job satisfaction by providing the evidence that procedural justice has a positive impact on job satisfaction. Although the context of younger supervisor-older subordinate in which this study is conducted is unique, the impact of procedural justice on job satisfaction is still confirmed even in this situation, although, it is suggested that organizational justice is a subjective phenomenon and the perception of fairness held by an individual varies in varying contexts (Johnson & Johnson, 2015). However, another important point which needs equal consideration is that this unique context led to the evidence of insignificant impact of distributive justice on job satisfaction of older subordinates.

Implications of the study

The present study extends the literature on relational demography theory by combining the projections of the similarity attraction paradigm to assess the impact of demographic dissimilarity in terms of age in the non-normative composition of supervisor-subordinate dyad. Relational demography theory suggests that employees show desirable work attitudes and behaviors when they work with demographically similar supervisor (Hom et al., 2009). For the purpose of analysis, another theory of leadership (LMX theory of leadership) was

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

incorporated in the model to see if leader-member exchange quality can offset the possible harms of the relational incongruence resulting from directional age difference between a younger supervisor and older subordinate.

The results of the study represent the trends which are associated with age diversity in the workplaces. The study can benefit the practitioners by helping them understand about how age dissimilarity in supervisor-subordinate dyad can affect the members of the dyad and organization as a whole. At minimum, the results of the study evidence how perceptions of dissimilarity can affect the older employees by adversely affecting their job satisfaction. To avoid the potential consequences of dissimilarity, organizations and policy makers can develop strategies to mitigate the possible effects of such non-normative team structures. Although much research is needed to be done, the present study still provides initial evidence that elements of the organizational climate specifically related to age such as ageism may moderate the behaviors of the older subordinates, however, on part of the organizations efforts can be made to transcend the feelings of social exclusion and discrimination by including the older subordinates in such additional tasks which represent autonomy and thus increase their self-worth.

Limitations of the study

The first limitation of the study lies in its geographical boundary which was limited to one province of Pakistan. Although, the study was conducted in Pakistan because there were constant calls of research (Kunze, 2017) to study the age diversity in the non-western countries but the topic of age inverse supervision is novel and its research in western countries is also not that primitive. So one limitation that this study poses is that its geographical boundary extends over Pakistan only and its generalizability to other countries may require more research. The two major reasons which kept the researcher limited to not address the hurdles mentioned above include:-

- The monetary constraints which limit the capacity of the researcher to bear the cost of personally reaching all the respondents who belonged to various different universities located in geographically dispersed regions of Punjab (Pakistan).
- The COVID-19 pandemic which was at its peak and people were restricted to maintain social distance through fewer contacts. All the educational institutes including Higher Educational Universities and the public transport were closed to avoid the harms of the pandemic.

Directions for Future Research

As it is expected that by 2025 the younger workforce will dominate to occupy most of the supervisory jobs at global level (Obmerga & Elarco, 2021) so the researcher believes that studying this non-traditional dyad from the perspective of older subordinates is not enough, therefore, future researchers may consider analyzing the aspects of younger supervisors which may be important for organizational success.

The present study analyzed the job satisfaction of the older subordinates by considering only age as a salient factor to categorize supervisor in relation to subordinate, however, a more liberal approach to categorize supervisor and subordinate can be utilized for future research. Older subordinate with a certain age will hold other categories of differentiation

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

simultaneously for example he may be a male or female etc. at the same time. The previous research also proposed that the impact of age salience varies for older workers of different ethnicity and gender categories.

The scope of the present research was limited to fully incorporate all the variables which may play a significant role in influencing the work outcomes of the older subordinates due to time and cost constraints. Future research can, however, extend the study model for empirical investigation of other important variables such as Emotional labor which can be tested for its possible moderation in the link of LMX relationship quality with job satisfaction of the older employees.

Also, the model of this study can be tested in other regions such as Arab countries which have adopted modern ways of diversity management to tackle the multi-cultural workforce constituted from different regions of the world as about 83.5% of the labor force of UAE is constituted of non-nationals (Laith et al., 2019). The model can also be tested in the non-western contexts where the culture is entirely different (Kicheva & Tatyana, 2017).

References

1. Abrams, D., Swift, H., & Drury, L. (2016). Old and Unemployable? How Age-Based Stereotypes Affect Willingness to Hire Job Candidates. *Journal of Social Issues*, 72, 105-121. doi:10.1111/josi.12158
2. Al-Zu'bi, H. (2010). A Study of Relationship between Organizational Justice and Job Satisfaction. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5, 102-109. doi:10.5539/ijbm.v5n12p102
3. Anand, S., Hu, J., Liden, R., & Vidyarthi, P. (2011). Leader-member exchange: Recent research findings and prospects for the future. In (pp. 311-325).
4. Bornay-Barrachina, M. d. M., & Guerrero-Villegas, J. (2014). *Diversity Role on LMX relationships*. Retrieved from <https://EconPapers.repec.org/RePEc:pab:wpboam:14.02>
5. Bos, J., Donders, N., Bouwman-Brouwer, K., & Gulden, J. (2009). Work characteristics and determinants of job satisfaction in four age groups: University employees' point of view. *International archives of occupational and environmental health*, 82, 1249-1259. doi:10.1007/s00420-009-0451-4
6. Cabelkova, I., Abrhám, J., & Strielkowski, W. (2015). Factors influencing job satisfaction in post-transition economies: The case of the Czech Republic. *International Journal of Occupational Safety and Ergonomics*, 21, 448-456. doi:10.1080/10803548.2015.1073007
7. Cappelli, Peter, & Novelli. (2010). *Managing the older worker: How to prepare for the new organizational order*. Harvard Business Press.
8. Cappelli, P., & Novelli, B. (2013). Managing the Older Worker: How to Prepare for the New Organizational Order. *NHRD Network Journal*, 6, 83-84. doi:10.1177/0974173920130414
9. Chiang, F., & Birtch, T. (2007). The transferability of management practices: Examining cross-national differences in reward preferences. *Human Relations - HUM RELAT*, 60, 1293-1330. doi:10.1177/0018726707082849
10. Cohen-Charash, Y., & Spector, P. (2001). *The Role of Justice in Organizations: A Meta-Analysis*.
11. Cohrs, J. C., Abele, A., & Dette, D. (2006). Integrating Situational and Dispositional Determinants of Job Satisfaction: Findings From Three Samples of Professionals. *The Journal of psychology*, 140, 363-396. doi:10.3200/JRLP.140.4.363-395
12. Fornell, C., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39-50. doi:10.2307/3151312
13. Ghazzawi, I. (2011). Does age matter in job satisfaction? The case of U.S. information technology professionals. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict*, 15, 25-54.
14. Glenn, Norval, Charles, & Weaver. (1985). Age, cohort, and reported job satisfaction in the United States. *Current Perspectives on Aging and the Life-cycle*, 89-109.
15. Golden, T., & Veiga, J. (2008). The impact of superior-subordinate relationships on the commitment, job satisfaction, and performance of virtual workers. *Leadership Quarterly*, 19, 77-88. doi:10.1016/j.leaqua.2007.12.009
16. Hair, J., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2013). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling: Rigorous

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

- Applications, Better Results and Higher Acceptance. *Long Range Planning*, 46, 1-12. doi:10.1016/j.lrp.2013.08.016
17. Henseler, J., Hubona, G., & Ray, P. (2016). Using PLS Path Modeling in New Technology Research: Updated Guidelines. *Industrial Management & Data Systems*, 116, 2-20. doi:10.1108/IMDS-09-2015-0382
 18. Henseler, J., Ringle, C., & Sinkovics, R. (2009). The Use of Partial Least Squares Path Modeling in International Marketing. In (Vol. 20, pp. 277-319).
 19. Henseler, J., & Sarstedt, M. (2013). Goodness-of-Fit Indices for Partial Least Squares Path Modeling. *Computational Statistics*, 28, 565-580. doi:10.1007/s00180-012-0317-1
 20. Hom, P., Tsui, A., Wu, J., Lee, T., Zhang, A., Fu, P., & Li, L. (2009). Explaining Employment Relationships With Social Exchange and Job Embeddedness. *The Journal of applied psychology*, 94, 277-297. doi:10.1037/a0013453
 21. Johnson, D., & Johnson, R. (2015). Cooperative Learning: Improving university instruction by basing practice on validated theory. *Journal on Excellence in College Teaching*, 25, 85-118.
 22. Khan, Salman Fazal, & Siddiqui, D. A. (2020). Transformational leadership and subordinate organizational commitment in pakistan: the complementary role of status incongruence and supervisor gender. *Journal of Business Strategies*, 14(2), 120.
 23. Kicheva, & Tatyana. (2017). Management of employees from different generations-Challenge for Bulgarian managers and HR professionals. *Economic Alternatives*(1), 103-121.
 24. Kollmann, T., Stoeckmann, C., Kensbock, J., & Peschl, A. (2019). What satisfies younger versus older employees, and why? An aging perspective on equity theory to explain interactive effects of employee age, monetary rewards, and task contributions on job satisfaction. *Human Resource Management*, 59. doi:10.1002/hrm.21981
 25. Kooij, D. T. A. M., Guest, D. E., Clinton, M., Knight, T., Jansen, P. G. W., & Dikkers, J. S. E. (2013). How the impact of HR practices on employee well-being and performance changes with age. *Human Resource Management Journal*, 23(1), 18-35. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/1748-8583.12000>
 26. Kulik, C., Ryan, S., Harper, S., & George, G. (2014). Aging Populations and Management. *The Academy of Management Journal*, 57, 929-935. doi:10.5465/amj.2014.4004
 27. Kunze, F., & Menges, J. (2017). Younger supervisors, older subordinates: an organizational-level study of age differences, emotions, and performance. doi:10.17863/CAM.12153
 28. Laith, A., Jameel, A., & Ahmad, A. R. (2019). The effect of organizational justice on job satisfaction among secondary school teachers. *International Review*, 82-90. doi:10.5937/intrev1903082L
 29. Lanier, & Dequies. (2021). Exploring Academic Leadership in Higher Education Through The Lens of Leader-to-Member Exchange (LMX) Theory.
 30. Lau, D., Lam, L., & Salamon, S. (2008). The Impact of Relational Demographics on Perceived Managerial Trustworthiness: Similarity or Norms? *The Journal of social psychology*, 148, 187-208. doi:10.3200/SOCP.148.2.187-209
 31. Lawrence, & Barbara. (1996). Organizational age norms: Why is it so hard to know one when you see one? *The Gerontologist* 36(2), 209-220.
 32. Leonardi, P. M., Huysman, M., & Steinfield, C. (2013). Enterprise Social Media: Definition, History, and Prospects for the Study of Social Technologies in Organizations. *Journal of Computer-Mediated Communication*, 19(1), 1-19. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/jcc4.12029>
 33. Levy, S. R., & Macdonald, J. L. (2016). Progress on Understanding Ageism. *Journal of Social Issues*, 72(1), 5-25. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1111/josi.12153>
 34. Lind, E., & Tyler, T. (1988). *The Social Psychology of Procedural Justice* (Vol. 18).
 35. Malangwasira, T. E. (2013). Demographic differences between a leader and followers tend to inhibit leader-follower exchange levels and job satisfaction. *Journal of Organizational Culture, Communications and Conflict*, 17, 63-106.
 36. Martinson, Brian, John, DeLeon, & Katherine. (2020). The Effect of an Aging Workforce on Perceptions of Satisfaction and Performance. *Journal of Managerial* 32(4).
 37. McCarthy, J., & Keegan, B. (2016). *The evaluation of social media use: A longitudinal study*.
 38. Miller, Carliss, & Orlando. (2020). Status incongruence in supervisor-subordinate dyads-the effects on subordinate job satisfaction and creative performance. *Journal of Business Strategies*, 37(2).
 39. Miller, R. K. (2020). Reflections—Richard Kermit Miller, PhD April 12, 2020. *Birth Defects Research*, 112(12), 929-932. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/bdr2.1704>

Analyzing the impact of age inverse relationship on the job satisfaction ...

40. Obmerga, & Elarco, M. (2021). For whom the bell (really) tolls: A grounded theory of millennial academic supervisors' sensemaking of communitarian values as a springboard to enrich their transformational leadership attributes. *International Journal of Leadership in Education* 1-33.
41. Peeters, Marga, & Loek. (2012). Demographic change across the globe-Maintaining social security in ageing economies. *World Economics* 13(2), 75-97.
42. Posthuma, R., & Campion, M. (2009). Age Stereotypes in the Workplace: Common Stereotypes, Moderators, and Future Research Directions†. *Journal of Management - J MANAGE*, 35, 158-188. doi:10.1177/0149206308318617
43. Reeves, & Michael. (2013). The challenges of young-typed jobs and how older workers adapt.
44. Smith, Wanda, & Vernard. (1994). Younger supervisor-older subordinate dyads: a relationship of cooperation or resistance? *Psychological Reports*, 74(3), 803-812.
45. Stephenson, & Jacqueline. (2017). The leader-member exchange (LMX) approach to age diversity. *Leading diversity in the 21st century*, 161-189.
46. Stöckmann, & Kensbock. (2020). What satisfies younger versus older employees, and why? An aging perspective on equity theory to explain interactive effects of employee age, monetary rewards, and task contributions on job satisfaction.
47. Suliman, A. (2007). Links between justice, satisfaction and performance in the workplace: A survey in the UAE and Arabic context. *Journal of Management Development*, 26, 294-311. doi:10.1108/02621710710740075
48. Tan, C. L., & Nasurdin, A. M. (2011). Human Resource Management Practices and Organizational Innovation: Assessing the Mediating Role of Knowledge Management Effectiveness. *The Electronic J. Knowledge Management*, 9, 155-167.
49. Wang, B., Zhang, S.-q., Dong, J.-l., Li, Y., Jin, Y.-x., Xiao, H.-w., . . . Cui, M. (2022). Ambient temperature structures the gut microbiota of zebrafish to impact the response to radioactive pollution. *Environmental Pollution*, 293, 118539. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envpol.2021.118539>
50. Wignall, P., & Best, J. (2004). Sedimentology and kinematics of a large, retrogressive growth-fault system in Upper Carboniferous deltaic sediments, western Ireland. *Sedimentology*, 51. doi:10.1111/j.1365-3091.2004.00673.x
51. Yakoub. (2008). *The ageing workforce and the leader-member exchange theory: The influence of need for leadership and the working relationship between employees*. University of Leiden, Netherlands.
53. Yang, J., & Matz-Costa, C. (2018). Age Diversity in the Workplace: The Effect of Relational Age Within Supervisor–Employee Dyads on Employees' Work Engagement. *The International Journal of Aging and Human Development*, 87(2), 156-183. doi:10.1177/0091415017709798